

Threats to the vulture population in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Vultures are on the verge of extinction in Bangladesh due to adverse environments. Once there were seven types of vultures in the country. Now, only the Bengal vulture is hardly seen. Therefore, the study aims to identify the threats to the vulture population in Bangladesh. It is revealed that the vulture in Bangladesh faces an onslaught of threats from veterinary painkilling drugs like Diclofenac and Ketoprofen. The supply of safe food has declined as the dead cattle are often buried or used as food in shrimp farms. The vulture is comfortable with floating carcasses on the wetlands more than the dead animals kept on the land. Due to the sharp decline of the wetlands, they face more competition from other scavengers like dogs to grab the food on the land. The illegal logging of tall trees, notably fan palms is destroying the roosting-nesting places for vultures. increased electricity coverage is causing more collision and electrocution, which is killing more vultures as the energy installations are not underpinned by sound bird-safe pole designs and correct siting. It was argued that the people of Bangladesh have a kind of adverse understanding of the vultures but they are not aware of the importance of the vulture conservation.

Keywords: Vultures in Bangladesh, habitat loss, fan palms, painkilling drug, diclofenac and ketoprofen

Introduction

Over the past few decades, the number of vultures in South Asian countries has been rapidly declining (Safford *et al.* 2019; Pain *et al.* 2008). Vultures play a critical role in maintaining the ecosystem by controlling the spread of diseases to humans. Unfortunately, 99.9% of the vultures in South Asia have disappeared in recent times (Lahkar *et al.* 2010; Prakash *et al.* 2007). Vultures cleanse the environment and contribute to maintaining the ecosystem. Vultures are on the way to extinction due to adverse environments, lack of preservation measures and food shortages.

According to the Forest Department of Bangladesh, there were 1,972 vultures in the country in 2008. In the last census conducted in 2015, that number fell to 260. Vultures are on the verge of extinction in Bangladesh due to adverse environments. Once there were seven types of vultures in the country. Now, only the Bengal vulture is hardly seen. Vultures can be rarely spotted in only two places: *Rema-Kalenga* Forest, and the Sundarbans.

Overpopulation pressure and widespread poverty caused massive forest fragmentation and biodiversity loss in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.* 2009; Rahman 2021; Rahman 2023 a, b, c, d, e, f). Habitat destruction and biodiversity loss go hand in hand here (Rahman 2023g, h, I, j). Therefore, the study aims to identify the threats to the vulture population in Bangladesh.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from the Forest Department. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders to identify the threats. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to find out the solutions. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Threats to vulture conservation in Bangladesh

Toxic food

The respondents opined that the vulture in Bangladesh faces an onslaught of threats from veterinary painkilling drugs. They are infected when they consume dead cattle which were provided with drugs like Diclofenac and Ketoprofen. Consequently, they lose their ability to fly

and die due to kidney failure. On the other hand, the decline of vultures has increased some diseases like rabies, anthrax, etc.

Lack of safe food

The respondents added that the lack of safe food is also pushing these birds closer to extinction. All the stale and rotting dead bodies in nature are eaten and cleaned by them. The supply of the carcass of animals has decreased due to increased urbanization and improved waste management. As a result, they face increased starvation. The dead cattle are often buried or used as food in shrimp farms causing food shortages for vultures and contributing to their decline.

Loss of wetlands

The respondents argued that the vultures like the floating carcasses on the wetlands more than the dead animals kept on the lands. They enjoy hegemony in the wetlands over the land as they do not compete with other scavengers like dogs in the wetlands. The wetlands in Bangladesh are declining sharply due to grabbing, increased sedimentations and building blockages on the canals.

Deforestation

The respondents also added that vultures build their nests in tall trees. The illegal logging of tall trees, notably fan palms is destroying the roosting-nesting places for vultures. They argued that rampant deforestation is one of the major threats to the vulture community in Bangladesh.

Increased electricity coverage

The respondents opined that increased electricity coverage is causing more collision and electrocution, which is killing more vultures as the energy installations are not underpinned by sound bird-safe pole designs and correct siting.

Lack of awareness and understanding

The respondents added that the people of Bangladesh have a kind of adverse understanding of the vultures but they are not aware of the importance of the vulture conservation.

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